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GLOBAL WARMING AS AN ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEM OF OUR TIME

YELEU ADIYA

Bachelor student of S. Seifullin Kazakh Agrotechnical Research University

Scientific supervisor: **BAIGOSHKAROVA MAGRISHAT IMANGALIEVNA**

Senior lecturer at S.Seifullin Kazakh Agro Technical Research University,
Astana, Kazakhstan

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается многогранная проблема глобального потепления, определяемого как постепенное повышение средней температуры Земли с глубоким воздействием на глобальные климатические системы. В ней определяются основные причины, различаются природные факторы (такие как солнечная и вулканическая активность) и доминирующие антропогенные факторы (включая выбросы парниковых газов, вырубку лесов и промышленную деятельность). Затем анализируются широкомасштабные последствия этого явления, от таяния ледников и экстремальных погодных явлений до угроз биоразнообразию, продовольственной безопасности и здоровью человека. Наконец, в статье обсуждаются потенциальные решения, подчеркивая необходимость комплексного подхода, сочетающего переход к возобновляемым источникам энергии, активное международное сотрудничество, примером которого являются такие соглашения, как Парижское соглашение, и индивидуальную ответственность в потреблении и использовании ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: Greenhouse gases, climate change, deforestation, renewable energy, Paris agreement.

Introduction

Global warming is the process of a gradual increase in the average temperature of the Earth, which has a significant impact on the planet's climate systems. In recent decades, this phenomenon has become one of the most acute environmental problems, attracting the attention of scientists, government agencies and public organizations around the world. Climate warming affects all areas of life, from natural ecosystems to economic processes and human health.

Global warming is the result of a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors. Natural processes such as solar activity and volcanic activity have an impact on climate, but modern warming is mainly attributed to human activity. The introduction of technology, the development of industry, increased traffic flow and deforestation have increased the "greenhouse effect", which has led to an accelerated increase in global temperatures.

Studying global warming is extremely important. It allows us to predict possible consequences for ecosystems, develop measures for human and animal adaptation, and develop strategies to reduce harmful effects on the climate.

Causes of global warming

The causes of global warming are divided into two large groups: natural and anthropogenic.

Natural causes

Natural factors cause gradual climate changes over millions of years. The main natural causes include:

- * Solar activity. Changes in the intensity of solar radiation affect the amount of heat entering the Earth. Periods of increased solar activity are accompanied by an increase in temperature on the planet.

- Volcanic activity. During volcanic eruptions, ash, sulfur compounds and other gases are released into the atmosphere. In the short term, this can cool the climate, but in the long term, it can change its balance and increase warming.

• Changes in the Earth's orbit. Small fluctuations in the orbit and tilt of the Earth's axis lead to a change in the distribution of sunlight on the planet, which affects the climatic conditions.

Although natural factors are important, modern global warming is mainly due to human activity.

Anthropogenic causes

Human activity in recent centuries has significantly increased the greenhouse effect. The main anthropogenic causes include:

• Greenhouse gas emissions. These include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrogen oxides (NO₂O), and others. They trap heat in the atmosphere and prevent it from escaping into space, causing the temperature to rise. The main sources are fuel combustion, industrial production, and the operation of vehicles.

• Deforestation. Forests absorb carbon dioxide, reducing its concentration in the atmosphere. Mass deforestation reduces the area of forests, increasing the concentration of CO₂.

• Industrial production and transport. The active development of factories, power plants, and automobiles has led to a significant increase in greenhouse gas emissions.

Thus, the main part of modern global warming is related to human activity, which makes the problem manageable with targeted action.

The effects of global warming

Global warming has an impact on nature, society and the economy.

Climate change

An increase in the average temperature causes noticeable changes in the climate:

* An increase in temperature. The average temperature on the planet is rising, which leads to changes in weather conditions and an increase in the number of abnormal phenomena such as heavy rains, droughts, hurricanes and typhoons.

• Melting glaciers. Glaciers in the Arctic and Antarctic are shrinking, leading to rising sea levels and the threat of coastal flooding.

• Extreme weather events. The frequency and intensity of natural disasters are increasing, posing a threat to human and animal life.

Impact on nature

Climate change has a negative impact on ecosystems:

• Species extinction. Animals and plants that are unable to adapt to the changed conditions may disappear.

• Ecosystem change. Disruption of biomes, migrations of animals and plants change the usual food chains.

• Degradation of soils and reservoirs. Warming affects soil fertility, reduces the amount of fresh water, and reduces crop yields.

Social and economic consequences

• Agriculture. Warming is changing climate zones, affecting yields and food security.

• Human health. An increase in temperature contributes to the spread of infectious diseases, heat stroke and cardiovascular problems.

• Economic losses. Natural disasters cause significant damage to infrastructure, industry, and housing, increasing reconstruction costs.

Ways to solve the problem

Solving the problem of global warming requires an integrated approach at the international, State and personal levels.

Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions

• Transition to renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and hydropower.

• Improving energy efficiency in industry, transport and the domestic sector.

• Reforestation and reduction of deforestation.

International cooperation

- International agreements such as the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement help coordinate countries' actions to reduce emissions.
- Joint scientific research and technology exchange make it possible to develop effective measures to combat global warming.

Personal responsibility

- The use of public transport, reducing the consumption of electricity and resources.
- Support environmental initiatives and increase environmental literacy.
- Responsible consumption and recycling of waste.

Conclusion

Considering the above, I believe that global warming is one of the most serious problems of our time, threatening ecosystems, the economy and human health. It requires immediate action at all levels: international, national and personal. Therefore, in order to minimize the negative impact, it is necessary to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, use renewable energy sources, restore forests and develop ecological culture. Only comprehensive and concerted efforts will allow us to preserve the planet for future generations and ensure the sustainable development of humankind.

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